

CAIRT-PerReC

CAIRT Phase A Mission Performance and
Requirement Consolidation (PerReC)
Activity

ESA/ESTEC contract 4000136480/21/NL/LF CCN1

Deliverable D-06

Product Validation Plan

Technical Note

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Reference Number: DEL-06-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.1

Status: Final

Version/revision: 1.1

Date: 23.10.2025

<i>ESA Study Contract Report</i>		
<i>ESA Contract</i> 4000136480/21/N L/LF CCN1	<i>Title</i> Product Validation Plan	<i>Contractor</i> Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
<i>Abstract</i>		
<p>This CAIRT Product Validation Plan (PVP) defines the strategy for validating the CAIRT Level-2 and higher-level data products. It identifies state-of-the-art approaches that will ensure independent geophysical validation of the CAIRT data products and the provision of traceable quality indicators enabling (i) the Agency and the CAIRT Team to verify the compliance of the CAIRT data quality with mission requirements, and (ii) users to judge the fitness of the data for their use case by themselves.</p> <p>This document identifies: (i) the approaches to be used later in the project for the validation of the Level-2(+) data and of their associated uncertainty estimates, (ii) the available standards and protocols of reference, and missing practices, if any, (iii) the Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRM), other independent observations, and modelling support needed for the validation of the data products, (iv) tools, campaigns, facilities, and infrastructures required for the validation activities, (v) the techniques, methods, and metrics needed to verify that the developed algorithms have geophysical meaning and that the developed data products meet CAIRT data quality requirements as set out in the CAIRT MRD, and (vi) any other aspect required to conduct a comprehensive product validation.</p> <p>This version of the PVP has been prepared for the PerReC Final Presentation of 21-22 October 2025. It includes responses to Mid-Term Review comments, latest updates on the measurement networks and satellite missions, and notes on helpful validation tools and infrastructures.</p>		
<p>The work described in this report was done under ESA contract. Responsibility for the contents resides with the author(s) or organisation(s) that prepared it.</p>		
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DOCUMENT INFO

Reviewer

Reviewer	Organisation Short Name	E-Mail
All WP leader		

Document Control

Document version #	Date	Changes Made/Comments
0.0	02.09.2024	First draft version
0.1	14.10.2024	Draft version delivered for Mid-Term Review (22-23.10.2024)
0.2	31.03.2025	Second draft version including response (in comment) to Mid-Term Review RIDs.
1.0	09.10.2025	Final version delivered for the PerReC Final Presentation of October 21-22, 2025, including handling of MTR comments, latest updates on validation measurements (networks and satellite missions), and notes on validation tools and infrastructures .
1.1	23.10.2025	This final version including feedback from PerReC Final Presentation.

Signature by issuing authority and/or lead author

CAIRT Level-2(+) Product Validation Plan

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1 Purpose and scope of this document

1.1 Identification of this document

This CAIRT Product Validation Plan (PVP) document version 1.0 is deliverable DEL-06-01 of the *CAIRT Phase A Mission Performance and Requirement Consolidation (PerReC)* Activity – CCN1 to ESA Contract No. 4000136480/21/NL/LF. It was prepared for the PerReC project Final Presentation of 21-22 October 2025. Compared to previous draft versions it includes responses to the Mid-Term Review (MTR) RIDs and additional material elaborated for the Report for Mission Selection (RfMS) delivered ahead of the Earth Explorer 11 (EE11) User Consultation Meeting (UCM) held in Prague on 9 July 2025.

1.2 Purpose of this document

The Earth Explorer 11 Candidate Mission Changing-Atmosphere Infra-Red Tomography Explorer (CAIRT) is an imaging infrared spectrometer to measure the vertical profile of a large number of trace gases, aerosols and atmospheric waves with unprecedented spatial resolution and at altitudes from about 5 up to 115 km. These observational data are more than ever necessary to improve knowledge of the coupling of atmospheric circulation, composition and regional climate change. CAIRT was selected by the European Space Agency as one of two candidate missions for the Earth Explorer 11 satellite, to undergo Phase A studies. Part of these studies, the present document aims at identifying an approach to the geophysical validation of the CAIRT Level-2 and higher-level data products and the verification of their fitness for primary scientific goals identified by the community.

1.3 Definition and scope of CAIRT Level-2(+) validation

The Quality Assurance for Earth Observation framework (QA4EO) [QA4EO] recommends that data and derived products of any EO mission shall have associated with them a set of fully traceable Quality Indicators (QI) enabling users to readily assess the fitness for purpose of the data. A particular objective of establishing QIs is to verify compliance of the data quality with mission and key user requirements. CAIRT mission and user requirements have been formulated in the Earth Explorer 11 Candidate Mission CAIRT Report for Assessment [ESA-CAIRT 2023] and are being further developed and consolidated by the current PerReC activity of reference. As a basis for the present document primary and secondary mission objectives from that document have been reproduced in Table 1, and primary geophysical data quality requirements in Table 2.

Part of the overall CAIRT performance and quality assessment activities, this CAIRT Product Validation Plan defines the strategy for deriving suitable Quality Indicators for the CAIRT Level-2a and Level-2b data products through geophysical validation activities. The Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) defines validation as the process of assessing the quality of the satellite data by independent means. Accordingly, the present document identifies state-of-the-art approaches that will ensure independent geophysical validation of the CAIRT data products and the provision of traceable quality indicators.

This document identifies:

- (i) the approaches to be used for the geophysical validation of the Level-2(+) data and of their associated uncertainty estimates,
- (ii) the available standards and protocols of reference, and missing practices, if any,
- (iii) the Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRM), other independent observations, and modelling support needed for the validation of the data products,
- (iv) tools, campaigns, facilities, and infrastructures required for the validation activities,
- (v) the techniques, methods, and metrics needed to verify that the developed algorithms have geophysical meaning and that the developed data products meet CAIRT data quality requirements,
- (vi) any other aspect required to conduct a comprehensive product validation.

Table 1 - CAIRT Mission Objectives(MO, [P] Primary and [S] Secondary) and their mapping to Science Objectives (SO, [R] Required and [C] contributing) (source: table 3.1 extracted from [ESA-CAIRT 2023])

ID	Objective	SO [R]	SO [C]
MO-P-1	Observe atmospheric circulation throughout the lower stratosphere via long-lived tracers (e.g., SF ₆ , CFC-11, CFC-12, HCFC-22, N ₂ O) and derived age-of-air with a total uncertainty of ≤ 0.5 years (≤ 0.25 years in monthly zonal means); and via suitable upper atmospheric tracers (CH ₄ , CO, temperature) up to the mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT).	1, 3	5
MO-P-2	Determine the global distribution of gravity wave momentum flux, gravity wave phase speed, direction, and drag exerted, for gravity waves in a range of ~ 100 to ~ 2000 km horizontal and down to ≤ 3 km vertical wavelengths, from the lower stratosphere into the mid-mesosphere.	2	3, 5
MO-P-3	Observe NO produced in the lower thermosphere and NO _x (NO, NO ₂) in the MLT during quiescent conditions and during geomagnetic storms, and quantify the total reactive nitrogen NO _y (NO _x , HNO ₃ , N ₂ O ₅ , ClONO ₂) throughout the stratosphere.	3	4, 5
MO-P-4	Quantify pollutants from biomass burning and anthropogenic origins (CO, PAN), sulfate aerosol and the atmospheric sulfur budget (H ₂ SO ₄ (l), SO ₂ , OCS) within the free troposphere and the lower stratosphere during background and enhanced conditions.	4	5
MO-P-5	Quantify the vertical and horizontal distribution of O ₃ and H ₂ O throughout the middle atmosphere, and with particular emphasis on resolving strong gradients and spatial features within the upper troposphere-lower stratosphere (UTLS).	5	3, 4, 1
MO-S-1	Characterise optically thin ice clouds (cirrus, polar mesospheric clouds) and related aerosol-ice nucleation (NH ₃ , NH ₄ NO ₃ (s)) and hydrological processes (via HDO, δD) throughout the UTLS (and polar upper mesosphere).	-	4, 5
MO-S-2	Provide continued altitude-resolved monitoring of ozone-depleting halogenated substances (e.g., ClO, BrONO ₂ , additional CFCs/HCFCs) and polar stratospheric clouds.	-	1, 4, 5
MO-S-3	Exploit the large spectral range needed for the mission to retrieve additional trace constituents, further supporting any of the above objectives and/or of interest in their own right (e.g., pollutants such as C ₂ H ₂ , C ₂ H ₄ , C ₂ H ₆ , HCOOH, CH ₃ OH, HCN, organic aerosols, volcanic ash, etc.)	-	all

Table 2 - Primary geophysical data quality requirements for CAIRT. Uncertainty requirements are expressed for an individual measurement. Mission objectives refer to Table 1. (source: table 4.2 extracted from [ESA-CAIRT 2023])

Product	MO	Regions	Total uncertainty		Unit	Vert. res. (km)		Hor. res (km)	
			(G)	(T)		(G)	(T)	(G)	(T)
T	all	FT – LM	1	2	K	1	2	50	200
		UM	2	5		2	4	200	400
		LT	10	30		4	7	200	400
H ₂ O	5	FT	5	10	%	1	2	100	200
		LS	5	10	%	1	3	100	200
		US	5	10	%	2	3	100	300
		LM	500	800	ppb	2	4	200	400
		UM	500	800	ppb	3	5	200	400
O ₃	5	FT	15	30	ppb	1	2	100	200
		LS	100	300		1	2	100	200
		US	100	300		2	3	100	200
		LM	50	100		2	4	200	300
		UM	100	300		2	5	200	400
CH ₄	1	LS	30	60	ppb	1	3	100	200
		US				2	3	100	200
		LM				2	4	200	300
SF ₆	1	LS	0.1	0.13	ppt	1	3	100	ZM
HCFC-22	1	LS	2	6	ppt	1	3	100	200
CFC-11	1	LS	10	25	ppt	1	3	100	200
CFC-12	1	LS	10	30	ppt	1	3	100	200
N ₂ O	1	LS	10	16	ppb	1	3	100	200
		US				2			
CO	1, 4	FT	20	30	ppb	1	2	100	200
		LS	20	30		1	2	100	200
		US	40	70		2	3	200	300
		LM	100	500		2	4	200	300
		UM	700	2000		3	5	200	400
		LT	2000	5000		4	7	200	400
NO	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	1	4	100	300
		US	0.2	1		2	4	200	300
		LM	2	20		2	4	200	300
		UM	100	600		3	5	200	400
		LT	5000	30000		3	5	200	400
NO ₂	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	1	3	100	300
		US	0.2	0.5		2	3	200	
		LM	2	5		2	4	200	
HNO ₃	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	1	3	100	300
		US	0.2	0.5		2	3	200	300
		LM	0.5	2		2	4	200	400
N ₂ O ₅	3	LS	0.2	0.5	ppb	1	3	100	300
		US				2		200	
ClONO ₂	3	LS	0.1	0.25	ppb	1	3	100	300
		US	0.2	0.5		2		200	
PAN	4	FT – LS	0.04	0.1	ppb	1	2	100	200
OCS	4	LS	0.05	0.15	ppb	1	2	100	200
SO ₂	4	LS	0.1	1	ppb	1	2	100	200
H ₂ SO ₄ (l)	4	LS	0.1	0.3	μm ³ /cm ³	1	2	100	200

Table 3 – Atmospheric regions or layers used in defining CAIRT measurement requirements, referred to in Table 2 (source: table 4.1 extracted from [ESA-CAIRT 2023]). The tropopause (TP) varies with latitude, from about 10-11 km at the poles up to 17-18 km at the equator.

Region	Code	Altitude range (km)
Free/Upper Troposphere	FT/UT	5 – TP
Lower Stratosphere	LS	TP – 30
Upper Stratosphere	US	30 – 50
Lower Mesosphere	LM	50 – 75
Upper Mesosphere	UM	75 – 95
Lower Thermosphere	LT	95 – 115

2 Reference documents, terms and definitions

2.1 CAIRT reference document

[ESA-CAIRT 2023] ESA (2023). Report for Assessment: Earth Explorer 11 Candidate Mission CAIRT, European Space Agency, Noordwijk, The Netherlands, ESA-EOPSM-CAIR-RP-4372, 122 pp.

2.2 Standards

[CEOS-DMSMM] WGISS Data Management and Stewardship Maturity Matrix, CEOS Working Group on Information Systems and Services / Data Stewardship Interest Group, CEOS.WGISS.DSIG.DSMM, Version 1.3, April 2020. <https://ceos.org/ourwork/workinggroups/wgiss/documents/>

[CEOS-FRM] Latest version of the CEOS-FRM framework available on the CEOS Cal/Val Portal at <https://calvalportal.ceos.org/> Concepts described in Goryl, P., Fox, N., Donlon, C., and Castracane, P., Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRMs): What Are They? Remote Sens. 2023, 15, 5017. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15205017>

[CEOSweb] Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS): general calibration and validation resources publicly available on <http://calvalportal.ceos.org>

[ISO:9100] ISO TS 9100:2018(en), Quality Management Systems – Requirements for Aviation, Space and Defense Organizations.

[ISO:19124-1] ISO TD 19124-1 Geographic information — Calibration and validation of remote sensing data and derived products — Part 1: Fundamentals.

[ISO:19159] ISO TS 19159-1:2014(en), Geographic information - Calibration and validation of remote sensing imagery sensors and data — Part 1: Optical sensors.

[GCOS-IP] The 2022 GCOS Implementation Plan, GCOS TD No. 244 – GOOS TD No. 272, © World Meteorological Organization 2022. Available online at: <http://library.wmo.int>

[GCOS-IR] The 2022 GCOS ECVs Requirements, GCOS TD No. 245, © World Meteorological Organization 2022. Available online at: <http://library.wmo.int>

[GUM] Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, 2008, Evaluation of measurement data — Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement (GUM), JGCM 100: 2008. Available online at <http://www.bipm.org/en/publications/guides/gum.html>

[INSP-IR] INSPIRE Data Specification on Atmospheric Conditions and Meteorological Geographical Features – Technical Guidelines, European Commission Joint Research Centre, Guidance document D2.8.III.13-14_v3.0, 10 December 2013. Available online at: <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/id/document/tg/ac>

[QA4EO] GEO-CEOS Quality assurance framework for Earth Observation (QA4EO): <http://qa4eo.org>

[QA4ECV-QA] Nightingale, J., F. Boersma, J.-P. Muller, S. Compennolle, J.-C. Lambert, S. Blessing, R. Giering, N. Gobron, I. De Smedt, P. Coheur, M. George, J. Schulz, and A. Wood, Quality Assurance Framework Development based on Six New ECV Data Products to Enhance User Confidence for Climate Applications, MDPI Remote Sensing, 2018, 10(8), 1254; doi:10.3390/rs10081254, 2018.

[VIM] Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology (JCGM/WG 2) 200:2012 & ISO/IEC Guide 99-12:2007, International Vocabulary of Metrology – Basic and General Concepts and Associated Terms (VIM). Available online at <http://www.bipm.org/en/publications/guides/vim.html>

2.3 Validation protocols and community practices

Cortesi, U., J.-C. Lambert, C. De Clercq, G. Bianchini, T. Blumenstock, A. Bracher, E. Castelli, V. Catoire, K. V. Chance, M. De Mazière, P. Demoulin, S. Godin-Beekmann, N. Jones, K. Jucks, C. Keim, T. Kerzenmacher, H. Kuellmann, J. Kuttippurath, M. Iarlori, G. Y. Liu, Y. Liu, I. S. McDermid, Y. J. Meijer, F. Mencaraglia, S. Mikuteit, H. Oelhaf, C. Piccolo, M. Pirre, P. Raspollini, F. Ravegnani, W. J. Reburn, G. Redaelli, J. J. Remedios, H. Sembhi, D. Smale, T. Steck, A. Taddei, C. Varotsos, C. Vigouroux, A. Waterfall, G. Wetzell, and S. Wood, Geophysical validation of MIPAS-Envisat operational ozone data, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 7, 4807-4867, 2007.

Dawkins, E. C. M., Feofilov, A., Rezac, L., Kutepov, A. A., Janches, D., Höffner, J., et al. (2018). Validation of SABER v2.0 operational temperature data with ground-based lidars in the mesosphere-lower thermosphere region (75–105 km). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 123, 9916–9934. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018JD028742>

De Longueville, H., L. Clarisse, S. Whitburn, C. Clerbaux, G. Lecomte, and P. Coheur, Atmospheric trends of long-lived halogenated gases derived from 15 years of IASI measurements, *J.Q.S.R.T.*, 311, doi:10.1016/j.jqsrt.2023.108755, 2023.

Hubert, D., Lambert, J.-C., Verhoelst, T., Granville, J., Keppens, A., Baray, J.-L., Bourassa, A. E., Cortesi, U., Degenstein, D. A., Froidevaux, L., Godin-Beekmann, S., Hoppel, K. W., Johnson, B. J., Kyrölä, E., Leblanc, T., Lichtenberg, G., Marchand, M., McElroy, C. T., Murtagh, D., Nakane, H., Portafaix, T., Querel, R., Russell III, J. M., Salvador, J., Smit, H. G. J., Stebel, K., Steinbrecht, W., Strawbridge, K. B., Stübi, R., Swart, D. P. J., Taha, G., Tarasick, D. W., Thompson, A. M., Urban, J., van Gijssel, J. A. E., Van Malderen, R., von der Gathen, P., Walker, K. A., Wolfram, E., and Zawodny, J. M.: Ground-based assessment of the bias and long-term stability of 14 limb and occultation ozone profile data records, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 9, 2497-2534, doi:10.5194/amt-9-2497-2016, 2016.

Keppens, A., Lambert, J.-C., Granville, J., Miles, G., Siddans, R., van Peet, J. C. A., van der A, R. J., Hubert, D., Verhoelst, T., Delcloo, A., Godin-Beekmann, S., Kivi, R., Stübi, R., and Zehner, C.: Round-robin evaluation of nadir ozone profile retrievals: methodology and application to MetOp-A GOME-2, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 8, 2093-2120, doi:10.5194/amt-8-2093-2015, 2015.

Keppens, A., Compennolle, S., Verhoelst, T., Hubert, D., and Lambert, J.-C.: Harmonization and comparison of vertically resolved atmospheric state observations: Methods, effects, and uncertainty budget, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 12, 4379–4391, doi:10.5194/amt-12-4379-2019, 2019.

Keppens, A., Compennolle, S., Hubert, D., Verhoelst, T., Granville, J., and Lambert, Removing Prior Information from Remotely Sensed Atmospheric Profiles by Wiener Deconvolution Based on the Complete Data Fusion Framework, *Remote Sensing*, 14(9), 2197; doi:10.3390/rs14092197, 2022.

Laeng, A.; Hubert, D.; Verhoelst, T.; von Clarmann, T.; Dinelli, B.M.; Dudhia, A.; Raspollini, P.; Stiller, G.; Grabowski, U.; Keppens, A.; Kiefer, M.; Sofieva, V.; Froidevaux, L.; Walker, K.; Lambert, J.-C.; Zehner, C., The ozone climate change initiative: Comparison of four Level-2 processors for the Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding (MIPAS), *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 162, 316-343, doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2014.12.013, 2015.

- Loew, A., W. Bell, L. Brocca, C. E. Bulgin, J. Burdanowitz, X. Calbet, R. V. Donner, D. Ghent, A. Gruber, T. Kaminski, J. Kinzel, C. Klepp, J.-C. Lambert, G. Schaepman-Strub, M. Schröder, and T. Verhoelst, Validation practices for satellite-based earth observation data across communities, *Rev. Geophys.*, 55, 779–817, doi: 10.1002/2017RG000562, 2017.
- Verhoelst, T., Granville, J., Hendrick, F., Köhler, U., Lerot, C., Pommereau, J.-P., Redondas, A., Van Roozendaal, M., and Lambert, J.-C.: Metrology of ground-based satellite validation: co-location mismatch and smoothing issues of total ozone comparisons, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 8, 5039-5062, doi:10.5194/amt-8-5039-2015, 2015.
- von Clarmann, T., C. De Clercq, M. Ridolfi, M. Höpfner, and J.-C. Lambert, The horizontal resolution of MIPAS, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 2, 47-54, 2009.
- von Clarmann, T., D. A. Degenstein, N. J. Livesey, S. Bender, A. Braverman, A. Butz, S. Compornolle, R. Damadeo, S. Dueck, P. Eriksson, B. Funke, M. C. Johnson, Y. Kasai, A. Keppens, A. Kleinert, N. A., Kramarova, A. Laeng, B. Langerock, V. H. Payne, A. Rozanov, T. O. Sato, M. Schneider, P. Sheese, V. Sofieva, G. P. Stiller, C. von Savigny and D. Zawada, 2020: Overview: Estimating and reporting uncertainties in remotely sensed atmospheric composition and temperature. *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 13, 4393-4436, doi:10.5194/amt-13-4393-2020.
- Zhou, M., Langerock, B., Vigouroux, C., Wang, P., Hermans, C., Stiller, G., Walker, K. A., Dutton, G., Mahieu, E., and De Mazière, M.: Ground-based FTIR retrievals of SF₆ on Reunion Island, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 11, 651–662, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-11-651-2018>, 2018.

2.4 Terms and definitions

This section identifies relevant standard terms and definitions published by normalization bodies: by BIPM/JCGM/ISO in their International Vocabulary of Metrology [VIM] and Guide to the Expression of Uncertainties [GUM], by ISO for terms related to Quality Management Systems [ISO:9100], and by the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) [CEOSweb, CEOS-FRM] and ISO [ISO:19124-1, ISO:19159] for specific terms related to the Cal/Val of Earth Observation data.

accuracy	closeness of agreement between a quantity value obtained by measurement and the true value of the measurand; note that it is not a quantity and it is not given a numerical quantity value [VIM]
ancillary data	mission-specific data obtained by other means than the instrument detectors and used in one or more mission-related processes. Ancillary data are typically of no or very little value out of the mission context.
auxiliary data	generic (i.e. non mission-specific) data used in one or more mission-related processes. Auxiliary data can be valuable outside the mission context.
bias	(1) systematic error of indication of a measuring system [VIM] (2) estimate of a systematic measurement error [VIM]
calibration	the process of quantitatively defining a system's response to known and controlled signal inputs [CEOSweb]
correlative measurement	independent measurement of a geolocated quantity that offers significant relationship with the satellite measurement of the same quantity to make them comparable and provide meaningful satellite validation results
error	(1) measured quantity value minus a reference quantity value [VIM] (2) difference of quantity value obtained by measurement and true value of the measurand [CEOSweb]
fiducial reference measurement	the suite of independent ground measurements that provide the maximum return on investment for a satellite mission by delivering, to users, the required confidence in data products, in the form of independent validation results and satellite measurement uncertainty estimation, over the entire end-to-end duration of a satellite mission [CEOS-FRM]
influence quantity	quantity that, in a direct measurement, does not affect the quantity that is actually measured, but affects the relation between the indication and the measurement result [VIM]
Level-0 data	reconstructed, unprocessed instrument and payload data at full space-time resolution, with all available supplemental information to be used in subsequent processing (e.g. ephemeris, atmospheric and calibration modes, housekeeping data, health and safety) [from ISO:19159]
Level-1a data	reconstructed unprocessed data at full resolution, time referenced, and annotated with ancillary information, including radiometric and geometric calibration coefficients and geo-referencing parameters (e.g. ephemeris) computed and appended but not applied to the L0 data [from ISO:19159]
Level-1b data	radiometrically corrected and calibrated, geo-located data in physical units at full instrument resolution as acquired [from ISO:19159]

Level-1c data	Level-1b data ortho-rectified, cloud-cleared, apodised, re-sampled to a specified geodetic grid (proposed by CEOS WGCV)
Level-2 data	derived geophysical parameters at the same resolution and geolocation as the Level-1 source data from which it is derived [adapted from ISO:19159]
Level-3 data	data or retrieved geophysical parameters (i.e. derived from Level-1 or 2 data products) which have been spatially and/or temporally re-sampled and mapped on uniform space-time grid scales, usually with some completeness and consistency. Such re-sampling may include averaging, compositing, kriging, use of Kalman filters... [from ISO:19159]
Level 4 data	model output or results from analyses of lower level data, i.e., parameters that are not directly measured by the instruments, but are derived from these measurements [ISO:19159]
measurand	quantity intended to be measured [VIM]
measurement bias	estimate of a systematic measurement error [VIM]
measurement error	measured quantity value minus a reference quantity value [VIM]
measurement uncertainty	non-negative parameter characterizing the dispersion of the quantity values being attributed to a measurand, based on the information used [VIM]
metrological traceability	property of a measurement result whereby the result can be related to a reference through a documented unbroken chain of calibrations, each contributing to the measurement uncertainty [VIM]
Phase E1	the commissioning phase of the satellite mission, starting at launch and covering the initial months of in-flight operation, over which the platform and instruments are switched on, functionally checked out, stabilized, and characterized. During this period a routine in-flight calibration scenario and the routine validation operations are to be consolidated.
Phase E2	the operational phase of the satellite mission, over which any instruments are assumed to operate in a stable measuring mode: routine instrument calibration and data product validation are performed. Only smaller changes to the instrument settings, measurement modes, and algorithm updates are expected.
precision	closeness of agreement between quantity values obtained by replicate measurements of a quantity on the same or similar object under specified conditions [VIM]
quality	(1) the totality of features and characteristics of a product or service that bears its ability to satisfy stated or implied needs [ISO:9100] (2) fitness-for-purpose [CEOSweb]
quality assurance (QA)	QA refers to the overall management of the processes involved in obtaining the data (CEOS/ISO); it is different from quality assessment and from quality control
quality control (QC)	QC refers to the activities undertaken to check and optimise accuracy and precision of the data after its collection (CEOS/ISO); it is different from quality assurance and from quality assessment.

quality indicator (QI)	a means of providing a user of data or derived product with sufficient information to assess its suitability for a particular application. This information should be based on a quantitative assessment of its traceability to an agreed reference or measurement standard (ideally SI), but can be presented as a numeric or a text descriptor, provided the quantitative linkage is defined.
random error	component of measurement error that in replicate measurements varies in an unpredictable manner; note that random measurement error equals measurement error minus systematic measurement error [VIM]
relative standard uncertainty	standard measurement uncertainty divided by the absolute value of the measured quantity value [VIM]
stability	(1) ability of a measuring system to maintain its metrological characteristics constant with time [VIM] (2) the maximum acceptable change in systematic error, usually per decade [GCOS-IP]
systematic error	component of measurement error that in replicate measurements remains constant or varies in a predictable manner [VIM]
uncertainty	non-negative parameter that characterizes the dispersion of the quantity values that are being attributed to a measurand, based on the information used [VIM]
validation	(1) the process of assessing, by independent means, the quality of the data products derived from the system outputs [CEOSweb] (2) verification where the specified requirements are adequate for an intended use [VIM]
verification	the provision of objective evidence that a given data product fulfils specified requirements; note that, when applicable, measurement uncertainty should be taken into consideration [VIM]

2.5 Acronyms and abbreviations

ACE	Atmospheric Chemistry Experiment
ACTRIS	(pan-European) Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure
AK	Averaging Kernel
ALTIUS	Atmospheric Limb Tracker for Investigation of the Upcoming Stratosphere
AO	Announcement of Opportunity
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
BASCOE	Belgian Assimilation System of Chemical Observations
CAIRT	Changing-Atmosphere Infra-Red Tomography Explorer
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CCI	Climate Change Initiative
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation Satellites
CLOUDNET	Cloud properties monitoring Network
CP	Commissioning Phase

C(T)H	Cloud (Top) Height
DFS	Degree of Freedom of the System
DIAL	Differential Absorption LIDAR
EARLINET	European Aerosol Research Lidar Network
EC	European Commission
ECC	Electro-chemical cell
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
ECV	Essential Climate Variable
Envisat	ESA's Environmental Satellite
EOS	Earth Observing System
ESA	European Space Agency
EU	European Union
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
EVDC	ESA Atmospheric Validation Data Centre
FOV	Field of view
FRM	Fiducial Reference Measurement
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infra-Red spectrometer
GAW	Global Atmosphere Watch
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GEO	Geostationary orbit
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
G3W	Global Greenhouse Gas Watch
GLORIA	Gimballed Limb Observer for Radiance Imaging of the Atmosphere
GOMOS	Global Ozone Monitoring by Occultation of Stars
GRUAN	GCOS Reference Upper Atmosphere Network
GUM	Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JCGM	Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology
JPSS	Joint Polar Satellite System
LEO	Low Earth orbit
LIDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
LOS	Line of Sight
MIPAS	Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding
MRD	Mission Requirement Document
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NDACC	Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change

NetCDF-CF	Network Common Data Form - Climate and Forecast conventions
NILU	Norsk Institutt for Luftforskning / Norwegian Institute for Air Research
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NRT	Near Real Time
OFFL	Off-line
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OMI	Ozone Monitoring Instrument
OMPS-LP	Ozone Mapper and Profiling Suite – Limb Profiler
OSCAR	WMO Observing Systems Capabilities Analysis and Review
OSSSMOSE	Observing System of Systems Simulator for Multi-mission Synergies Experiments
PDGS	Payload Data Ground Segment
PRF	Product Readme File
PUM	Product User Manual
PV	Potential vorticity
QA	Quality Assurance
QA4EO	Quality Assurance framework for Earth Observation
QC	Quality Control
QI	Quality Indicator
RT	Real Time
S5P	Sentinel-5 Precursor
SAA	South Atlantic Anomaly
SCIAMACHY	SCanning Imaging Absorption spectroMeter for Atmospheric CHartographY
SHADOZ	Southern Hemisphere ADditional OZonesonde programme
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SPE	Solar Proton Event
Suomi-NPP	Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership
SZA	Solar Zenith Angle
TROPOMI	Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument
TUNER	Towards Unified Error Reporting
UARS	Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite
UTLS	Upper Troposphere / Lower Stratosphere
VIM	International Vocabulary of Metrology
WCRP	World Climate Research Programme
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
WOUDC	World Ozone and Ultraviolet Data Centre
WWW	World Weather Watch

3 Standards and protocols

3.1 Frameworks

3.1.1 Quality Assurance framework for Earth Observation (QA4EO)

The Quality Assurance for Earth Observation framework (QA4EO) [QA4EO] is a set of guidelines elaborated by the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) under mandate of the Group on Earth Observations (GEO) to facilitate the development of a Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS) delivering comprehensive and timely knowledge/information products worldwide. This can only be achieved through the synergistic use of data derived from a variety of sources (satellite, airborne and in situ) and the coordination of the resources and efforts engaged. Starting from a system of disparate EO systems that were built for a multitude of applications, the QA4EO guidelines aim at facilitating interoperability and harmonization.

The cardinal principle of QA4EO is that data and derived products shall have associated with them a set of fully traceable Quality Indicators (QI) enabling users to readily assess the fitness for purpose of the data. QI shall be based on a documented and quantifiable assessment of evidence demonstrating the level of traceability to internationally agreed (where possible SI) reference standards. In particular, the objective of establishing QIs is also to verify compliance with mission and key user requirements, as well as the inter-mission consistency of the products, in order to ensure interoperability with and within the GEOSS and to enhance the relevance of the mission data for science and policy.

The QA4EO framework provides a set of guides to establishing quality indicators, to the content of a documentary framework, to reference standards, to comparisons, to establishing validated models and algorithms, to the expression of uncertainty of measurements, and to establishing quantitative evidence of traceability [QA4EO]. Compliance with several QA4EO guidelines (e.g., documentary framework) can be checked through the QA system developed for the generation of Climate Data Records in the context of the EC FP7 QA4ECV project ([QA4ECV-QA], Nightingale et al., 2018).

3.1.2 Calibration and validation – CEOS definitions and scope

Several CAIRT Level-2(+) data Quality Indicators can be derived from calibration, validation, and verification activities.

3.1.2.1 Calibration

CEOS defines calibration as the process of quantitatively defining a system's response to known and controlled signal inputs. Calibration of atmospheric composition satellites usually combines pre-launch calibration key data (CKD) with calibration measurements updated regularly in flight. The CAIRT Level-1 data processing takes the corrected and resampled interferograms (Level-0 data) and produces calibrated and geo-located spectral radiances by Fourier transform. The Level-1b includes a list of calibration tasks ensuring the quality of the spectrally resolved radiance profiles. Calibration and validation of the calibration (referred to as calibration validation by ISO:19159) are out of scope of the present document, nevertheless, their accurate output is a prerequisite to efficient validation activities.

3.1.3 Validation

CEOS defines validation as the process of assessing the data quality by independent means, also in a fully traceable way. Validation of Level-2 data involves a list of tasks:

- validation of the geophysical data: evaluation of quality indicators based on comparisons of the measurand values with respect to external reference data, over the entire domain of intended application, and over the full range of its main influencing quantities,
- assessment of the efficiency of quality flags and of data screening/usage recommendations on the validation-derived quality indicators,
- *ex-post* validation of the theoretical *ex-ante* uncertainty estimates calculated by the instrument experts and data producers and usually found in the data files or in associated product documentation (e.g., ATBD),
- external quality assessment of major data generation steps and modules where possible, including independent validation of the ancillary and auxiliary data used in the retrieval: assumed vertical profile of the measurand, of the interfering species, of temperature and of pressure, surface emissivity, cloud parameters, aerosol load...
- verification of compliance of actual data quality with product specifications (data content, coverage, resolution...), mission requirements, and core user requirements if available.

3.1.3.1 Verification

Between calibration and validation activities, another family of tasks are essential: these are the verification tasks, undertaken to provide objective evidence that the data product fulfils specified requirements. Verification includes statistical and visual monitoring that the data, intermediate parameters and ancillary parameters behave as expected. It also includes technical checks of the continuity of data dissemination and the proper and complete formatting of the data products. Verification is an operational duty better performed at the level of the Payload Data Ground Segment (PDGS) directly, at the end of the production chain, before dissemination and validation of the data. Like calibration this is also an activity out of scope of the present document, but its output and the resulting control measures are prerequisites to efficient validation activities.

3.1.3.2 CEOS-FRM Maturity Assessment Framework

The CEOS Working Group on Calibration and Validation (WGCV) has developed the CEOS-FRM Maturity Assessment Framework (Goryl *et al.*, 2023) CEOS-FRM. The label ‘CEOS Fiducial Reference Measurement’ (CEOS-FRM) acknowledges a level of maturity and adequacy of a reference measurement for the Cal/Val of a given class of satellite data. The CEOS-FRM assessment process is based on a maturity matrix that provides a visual assessment of the state of any candidate FRM against each of a set of given criteria. The process consists of a self-assessment followed by an independent verification, concluding with an indicative classification from A (excellent for the targeted class of sounders) to D (with severe weaknesses as a FRM for the targeted class of sounders). The criteria cover the following principles:

- traceability of the uncertainty of the FRM,
- independence of the FRM from the data that are to be validated,
- availability of an uncertainty budget of the FRM,
- availability of documented protocols for measurements and data management,
- accessibility of FRM,
- representativeness of FRM for the measurand that is to be validated,
- adequacy of the uncertainty of the FRM in view of the targeted uncertainty of the data that are to be validated, and
- utility of the FRM for a class of satellite data.

The following table details the criteria considered in the self-assessment and independent verification processes (table reproduced from the CEOS-FRM Maturity Assessment Framework guidelines version 2, maintained on <https://calvalportal.ceos.org/web/guest/frms-assessment-framework>).

Self-Assessment						Independent Assessor
Nature of FRM	FRM Instrumentation	Operations/ Sampling (single instrument)	Data	Metrology	Completeness, coverage and distribution	Verification
Descriptor	Instrument documentation	Automation level	Data completeness	Uncertainty characterisation	Validation capacity	Guidelines adherence
Location/ availability of FRM	Evidence of traceable calibration	Measurand sampling/ representativeness	Availability and Usability	Traceability documentation	Geographical coverage Temporal sampling	Utilisation/ Feedback
Range of sensors	QA Maintenance	ATBDs on processing/software	Data format	Comparison/ calibration of FRM	Centralized data, processing, quality assessment and adherence to community standards	Metrology verification
Complementary observations	Operator expertise	Guidelines on transformation to satellite sensor	Ancillary data	Adequacy for class of instrument/ measurand	Timeliness	Independent verification
FRM CLASSIFICATION						A B C D

3.2 Validation protocols and community practices

The following standards, protocols and guidelines are of interest to the CAIRT validation.

3.2.1 Validation practices across EO domains

Generic validation principles, methods and metrics applicable to all EO domains

Loew, A., W. Bell, L. Brocca, C. E. Bulgin, J. Burdanowitz, X. Calbet, R. V. Donner, D. Ghent, A. Gruber, T. Kaminski, J. Kinzel, C. Klepp, J.-C. Lambert, G. Schaepman-Strub, M. Schröder, and T. Verhoelst, **Validation practices for satellite based earth observation data across communities**, *Rev. Geophys.*, 55, 779–817, doi:10.1002/2017RG000562, 2017.

further formalized into

ISO TD ISO:19124-1, **Calibration and validation of remote sensing data and derived products – Part 1: Fundamentals**, 2023.

3.2.2 Round-robin and validation protocols for remotely sensed data

Generic round-robin and validation protocol

Keppens, A., J.-C. Lambert, J. Granville, G. Miles, R. Siddans, J. van Peet, R. van der A, D. Hubert, T. Verhoelst, A. Delcloo, S. Godin-Beekmann, R. Kivi, R. Stübi, and C. Zehner, **Round-robin evaluation of nadir ozone profile retrievals: Methodology and application to MetOp-A GOME-2**, Special issue “GOME-2: calibration, algorithms, data products and validation”, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 8, 2093-2120, doi:10.5194/amt-8-2093-2015, 2015.

Keppens, A., Compennolle, S., Verhoelst, T., Hubert, D., and Lambert, J.-C.: **Harmonization and comparison of vertically resolved atmospheric state observations: Methods, effects, and uncertainty budget**, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 12, 4379–4391, doi:10.5194/amt-12-4379-2019, 2019

MIPAS and ACE-FTS validation community practices

Cortesi, U., J.-C. Lambert, C. De Clercq, G. Bianchini, T. Blumenstock, A. Bracher, E. Castelli, V. Catoire, K. V. Chance, M. De Mazière, P. Demoulin, S. Godin-Beekmann, N. Jones, K. Jucks, C. Keim, T. Kerzenmacher, H. Kuellmann, J. Kuttippurath, M. Iarlori, G. Y. Liu, Y. Liu, I. S. McDermid, Y. J. Meijer, F. Mencaraglia, S. Mikuteit, H. Oelhaf, C. Piccolo, M. Pirre, P. Raspollini, F. Ravegnani, W. J. Reburn, G. Redaelli, J. J. Remedios, H. Sembhi, D. Smale, T. Steck, A. Taddei, C. Varotsos, C. Vigouroux, A. Waterfall, G. Wetzels, and S. Wood, **Geophysical validation of MIPAS-Envisat operational ozone data**, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, Vol. 7, 4807-4867, 2007.

Ridolfi, M., U. Blum, B. Carli, V. Catoire, S. Ceccherini, H. Claude, C. De Clercq, K. H. Fricke, F. Friedl-Vallon, M. Iarlori, P. Keckhut, B. Kerridge, J.-C. Lambert, Y. J. Meijer, L. Mona, H. Oelhaf, G. Pappalardo, M. Pirre, V. Rizi, C. Robert, D. Swart, T. von Clarmann, A. Waterfall, and G. Wetzels, **Geophysical validation of temperature retrieved by the ESA processor from MIPAS/ENVISAT atmospheric limb-emission measurements**, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 7, 4459-4487, 2007.

Sica, R. J., M. R. M. Izawa, K. A. Walker, C. Boone, S. V. Petelina, P. S. Argall, P. Bernath, G. B. Burns, V. Catoire, R. L. Collins, W. H. Daffer, C. De Clercq, Z. Y. Fan, B. J. Firanski, W. J. R. French, P. Gerard, M. Gerding, J. Granville, J. L. Innis, P. Keckhut, T. Kerzenmacher, A. R. Klekociuk, E. Kyrö, J.-C. Lambert, E. J. Llewellyn, G. L. Manney, I. S. McDermid, K. Mizutani, Y. Murayama, C. Piccolo, P. Raspollini, M.

- Ridolfi, C. Robert, W. Steinbrecht, K. B. Strawbridge, K. Strong, R. Stübi, and B. Thurairajah, **Validation of the Atmospheric Chemistry Experiment (ACE) version 2.2 temperature using ground-based and space-borne measurements**, *Atmo. Chem. Phys.*, 8, 35-62, 2008
- Dupuy, E., K. A. Walker, J. Kar, C. D. Boone, C. T. McElroy, P. F. Bernath, J. R. Drummond, R. Skelton, S. D. McLeod, R. C. Hughes, C. R. Nowlan, D. G. Dufour, J. Zou, F. Nichitiu, K. Strong, P. Baron, R. M. Bevilacqua, T. Blumenstock, G. E. Bodeker, T. Borsdorff, A. E. Bourassa, H. Bovensmann, I. S. Boyd, A. Bracher, C. Brogniez, J. P. Burrows, V. Catoire, S. Ceccherini, S. Chabrillat, T. Christensen, M. T. Coffey, U. Cortesi, J. Davies, C. De Clercq, D. A. Degenstein, M. De Mazière, P. Demoulin, J. Dodion, B. Firanski, H. Fischer, G. Forbes, L. Froidevaux, D. Fussen, P. Gerard, S. Godin-Beekmann, F. Goutail, J. Granville, D. Griffith, C. S. Haley, J. W. Hannigan, M. Höpfner, J. J. Jin, A. Jones, N. B. Jones, K. Jucks, A. Kagawa, Y. Kasai, T. E. Kerzenmacher, A. Kleinböhl, A. R. Klekociuk, I. Kramer, H. Küllmann, J. Kuttippurath, E. Kyrölä, J.-C. Lambert, N. J. Livesey, E. J. Llewellyn, N. D. Lloyd, E. Mahieu, G. L. Manney, B. T. Marshall, J. C. McConnell, M. P. McCormick, I. S. McDermid, M. McHugh, C. A. McLinden, J. Mellqvist, K. Mizutani, Y. Murayama, D. P. Murtagh, H. Oelhaf, A. Parrish, S. V. Petelina, C. Piccolo, J.-P. Pommereau, C. E. Randall, C. Robert, C. Roth, M. Schneider, C. Senten, T. Steck, A. Strandberg, K. B. Strawbridge, R. Sussmann, D. P. J. Swart, D. W. Tarasick, J. R. Taylor, C. Tétard, L. W. Thomason, A. M. Thompson, M. B. Tully, J. Urban, F. Vanhellefont, C. Vigouroux, T. von Clarmann, P. von der Gathen, C. von Savigny, J. W. Waters, J. C. Witte, M. Wolff, and J. M. Zawodny, **Validation of ozone measurements from the Atmospheric Chemistry Experiment (ACE)**, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 9, 287-343, 2009
- Hubert, D., J.-C. Lambert, T. Verhoelst, J. Granville, A. Keppens, J.-L. Baray, U. Cortesi, D. A. Degenstein, L. Froidevaux, S. Godin-Beekmann, K. W. Hoppel, E. Kyrölä, T. Leblanc, G. Lichtenberg, C. T. McElroy, D. Murtagh, H. Nakane, J. M. Russell III, J. Salvador, H. G. J. Smit, K. Stebel, W. Steinbrecht, K. B. Strawbridge, R. Stübi, D. P. J. Swart, G. Taha, A. M. Thompson, J. Urban, J. A. E. van Gijssels, P. von der Gathen, K. A. Walker, E. Wolfram, and J. M. Zawodny, **Ground-based assessment of the bias and long-term stability of fourteen limb and occultation ozone profile data records**, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 9, 2497-2534, doi:10.5194/amt-9-2497-2016, 2016
- von Clarmann, T., C. De Clercq, M. Ridolfi, M. Höpfner, and J.-C. Lambert, **The horizontal resolution of MIPAS**, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 2, 47-54, 2009.

Validation strategies for gravity wave (momentum flux) data

- Hertzog, A., V. Kopp, S. Wüst, M. Bittner, V. Sofieva, M. Gerding, P. Preusse, W. Lahoz, and M. Pulido, **ESA Gravity Wave Study - Validation strategies Task Report**, 72 pp., December 2011.

Best practices for aerosol, cloud and precipitation profile validation with CAIRT relevance

- Amiridis, V., Marinou, E., Hostetler, C., Koopman, R., Cecil, D., Moisseev, D., Tackett, J., Groß, S., Baars, H., Redemann, J., Marenco, F., Baldini, L., Tanelli, S., Fielding, M., Janiskova, M., Tanaka, T., O'Connor, E., Fjaeraa, A. M., Paschou, P., ... Kollias, P. (2025). **Best Practice Protocol for the validation of Aerosol, Cloud, and Precipitation Profiles (ACPPV) (Version 2)**. Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.15025627

3.3 Validation metrics

- von Clarmann, T., C. De Clercq, M. Ridolfi, M. Höpfner, and J.-C. Lambert, **The horizontal resolution of MIPAS**, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 2, 47-54, 2009.

- Verhoelst, T., F. Hendrick, U. Köhler, C. Lerot, J.-P. Pommereau, A. Redondas, M. Van Roozendael, and J.-C. Lambert, **Metrology of ground-based satellite validation: co-location mismatch and smoothing issues of total ozone comparisons**, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 8, 5039-5062, doi:10.5194/amt-8-5039-2015, 2015.
- von Clarmann, T. D. A. Degenstein, N. J. Livesey, S. Bender, A. Braverman, A. Butz, S. Compernelle, R. Damadeo, S. Dueck, P. Eriksson, B. Funke, M. C. Johnson, Y. Kasai, A. Keppens, A. Kleinert, N. A. Kramarova, A. Laeng, B. Langerock, V. H. Payne, A. Rozanov, T. O. Sato, M. Schneider, P. Sheese, V. Sofieva, G. P. Stiller, C. von Savigny, and D. Zawada, **Overview: Estimating and reporting uncertainties in remotely sensed atmospheric composition and temperature**, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 13, 4393-4436, doi:10.5194/amt-13-4393-2020, 2020. [SPARC TUNER]
- Keppens, A., Compernelle, S., Verhoelst, T., Hubert, D., Granville, J., and Lambert, J.-C.: **Removing Prior Information From Remotely Sensed Atmospheric Profiles by Wiener Deconvolution Based on the Complete Data Fusion Framework**, *Remote Sensing*, 14, 2197, doi:10.3390/rs14092197, 2022.

4 Validation approach

4.1 Requirements for CAIRT data products

To be able to carry out a comprehensive geophysical validation of the CAIRT Level-2 data products according to applicable standards and best practices, the following groups and variables are required:

- spatiotemporal and geometrical information about the time and location of the retrieval (time, longitude, latitude, altitude), and measurement and spacecraft angles and parameters,
- the retrieved profile of temperature and of concentration of the target chemical species,
- the *ex-ante* uncertainty estimate (error bar) associated with the retrieved profile concentration, with distinction of the systematic and random components of the uncertainty,
- first guess and a priori profiles, covariance and regularisation matrices, vertical averaging kernel matrix,
- aerosol profile retrieved as intermediate parameters for the profile retrieval of temperature and chemical species (if used),
- relevant quality indexes (vertical smoothness, retrieved information content...) and the aggregated quality flag combining these indexes,
- traceability of auxiliary parameters (including reference atmospheres) and of the retrieval.

4.2 Generic validation approach

4.2.1 Comparison to correlative measurements

The primary task of geophysical validation consists in the comparison of atmospheric composition satellite data to correlative measurements of sufficiently similar air masses and with documented measurement process and uncertainties. Comparison studies should be planned to involve a statistically significant number of data pairs to enable the derivation of robust, meaningful statistical estimates of the systematic difference and dispersion between the satellite and correlative measured quantity values, and of their behaviour with respect to time and to other relevant parameters: presence of (quasi)periodic oscillations and non-periodic changes, vertical and geographical patterns, dependence on influence quantities, influence of ancillary parameters of the retrieval process, long-term stability...

4.2.1.1 Ground-based monitoring networks

The geophysical validation of atmospheric composition satellites makes intensive use of the measurements acquired by ground- and balloon-based monitoring networks, several of them contributing to WMO's Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) and/or Global Climate Observing System (GCOS). Designed originally for the operational measurement of atmospheric composition, weather and climate variables, their data, associated documentation and distribution infrastructures currently reach CEOS-FRM maturity levels of Class A, B or C depending on the considered criteria:

- The measurement process and associated uncertainties are traceable to community-endorsed practices,
- The measurement and the geophysical quantity retrieval process are independent from the satellite data to be validated,

- Depending on the instrument and the species, the network data has associated with it a complete uncertainty budget, or at least uncertainty estimates, provided in the data files or in a separate document,
- Instruments contributing to e.g. WMO's Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) and/or Global Climate Observing System (GCOS), acquire measurements through official Standard Operating Procedures (SOP); all networks provide documented protocols for the measurement and for data management,
- The data is accessible through public (official archival) or semi-public (fast delivery of preliminary data) central data archives performing formal QA/QC checks,
- Representativeness of individual measurements is probably the most critical point, see paragraph below,
- The uncertainty of the network data usually is better than, or equivalent to the targeted uncertainty of the satellite data to be validated, and
- Several monitoring networks have proven their value as an essential source of information for the evaluation of satellite data quality for the class of satellite data to which CAIRT belongs.

In the atmospheric domain, criteria of representativeness are particularly important and complex. The ideal Fiducial Reference Measurement should offer the same perception of the 4D atmospheric field as that captured by the satellite instrument: same vertical sensitivity (thus, same vertical Averaging Kernels), same horizontal and temporal resolution, same solar local time... In reality, similarity in representativeness is achievable only to some degree, and often after averaging and smoothing of the correlative and/or the satellite data. Where possible, irreducible representativeness differences remaining after optimisation of the co-location and smoothing processes should be quantified.

4.2.1.2 Cross-validation with other satellites

By definition of what constitutes a Fiducial Reference Measurement for satellite validation [Goryl et al., 2023], it is understood that satellite-to-satellite comparisons cannot, *stricto sensu*, be considered as an independent validation. Nevertheless, satellite-to-satellite comparisons are essential to extend FRM-based validation to the global domain. Indeed, local and ground-based by nature, FRM-based validation cannot – or hardly – access several types of spatial patterns, temporal signals, and other features like internal inconsistencies.

For stratospheric and mesospheric data, cross-validation of satellites is required for:

- validation of Level-2 data over geographical areas not equipped with ground-based instrumentation,
- validation of Level-2 data over altitude ranges to which ground-based instruments are not – or hardly – sensitive, and at vertical resolution not always achievable by ground-based instrumentation,
- validation of Level-2 data for atmospheric states and influence quantities not covered by existing deployment of ground-based instruments,
- detection of internal inconsistencies like along-track biases (structures in bias and in noise, jumps between latitude zones due to changes in a priori...), sunrise/sunset biases, ...
- detection of Level-2 data outliers associated with inhomogeneous influence of surface albedo and cloud albedo (e.g., reflection or scattering effects),

- determination of the amplitude and geographical extent of perturbations linked e.g. to the South Atlantic Anomaly (SAA) and to solar proton events (SPE),
- validation of special events with spatio-temporal extent and evolution, e.g., effects of volcanic eruptions on ozone and on its measurement, aerosol plumes due to large fires.

4.2.1.3 Dedicated campaigns

Validation usually relies on ground-based instruments contributing to established monitoring networks and programmes, and on data from other satellites. While these measurement systems can provide observations of a few key parameters on a more or less cyclic mode, e.g. with a regular measurement frequency or with a regular latitude-time sampling, they do not cover the full portfolio of species and parameters targeted by CAIRT, nor its vertical resolution capabilities. Field measurement campaigns, on the other hand, offer access – during a shorter time period – to a wider list of variables enabling the required in-depth validation of the Level-2 data and derived products and their data processing, including uncertainties related to the influence quantities, ancillary parameters, and auxiliary parameters. They can also serve as a traceable transfer between satellite missions in case of a time gap.

Validation campaigns classically combine complementary instrumentation operating from different platforms: fixed and mobile instrumentation on the ground, aircrafts, balloons, and ad hoc modelling support (e.g., SCIAMACHY campaigns in PETERS et al., 2006, and Sentinel-5P validation campaigns). Campaigns can be organized in various types of environments offering access to different atmospheric states, measurement conditions, temperature, surface albedo ... and thereby complete the network-based validation and cross-validation of satellites with ranges of measurand and influence quantities not addressed yet. Where designed accordingly, validation campaigns can also give access to sub-measurement effects, e.g., vertical and horizontal smoothing errors associated with the low-resolution measurement of high-resolution structures and variability.

4.2.2 Modelling support

For the same reasons as mentioned in the previous subsection on satellite cross-validation, assessments based on numerical modelling can extend FRM-based comparison results to the global domain and to the detection of out-of-reach features. It is nonetheless understood that modelling output can obviously not be considered as a reference measurement.

In addition to what satellite data intercomparisons can offer, comparisons to models, and ingestion of the satellite data into a data assimilation system, allow the assessment of other quality aspects like the internal consistency of the satellite data set and among its different observation modes, the efficiency of the quality flags and data usage recommendations provided with the data products, the influence of diurnal cycle effects on the data comparisons etc. Direct feedback from data assimilation systems and operational services making use of the Level-2 data is also an important source of quality information (e.g., VISCARDY et al., 2010, for the BASCOE based evaluation of UARS MLS ozone data, and INNESS et al., 2019, for the CAMS based evaluation and monitoring of Sentinel-5P TROPOMI ozone data).

Interpretation of the comparisons to FRMs and to satellite data can also be supported by Observing System Simulation Experiments (OSSE) with multi-dimensional description of the observation operators of the different measurements. Such studies are helpful to validate independently the ex-ante uncertainty

estimates and better interpret the data comparison results (Lambert et al., 2012; Verhoelst et al., 2015). They are essential for the closure of the error budget of comparisons (see next section), and even critical when the number of co-located data pairs is poor, e.g. during the commissioning phase of a mission or during a field campaign limited in time.

4.2.3 Comparison to alternative retrievals

A special case lying between Level-2 data verification and satellite cross-validation consists in the comparison of Level-2 data retrieved from the same Level-1b data of the same satellite, but with an alternative Level-1-to-2 retrieval algorithm. Such an exercise is essential in identifying the sensitivity of Level-2 data quality to different auxiliary data, assumptions and approximations in the retrieval process. The outcome of studies based on alternative retrievals sheds complementary lights on Level-1 and Level-2 data quality and helps the interpretation of Level-2 data comparisons using on ground-based and satellite observations as a reference

4.2.4 Validation of the Level-2b data products

Validation of the CAIRT Level-2b data products constitutes a particular challenge as these higher-level quantities are the result of a specific processing involving several products and external data and are not directly measurable by independent means.

4.2.4.1 Reactive nitrogen budget (NO_y)

Verification of the budget of reactive nitrogen compounds (NO_y) derived from CAIRT data can make use of complementary measurements of the important nitrogen oxides, e.g., by (ground-, air- or space-based) FTIR spectrometers and (balloon-/air-based) gas chromatography. These measurements and their interest for NO_y validation are introduced in Section 5 of the document. The validation of NO_y downward transport observations requires a vertical resolution that can be offered by limb-viewing satellites (e.g., ACE-FTS and SABER) and by airborne experiments like GLORIA, but it is not achievable by the ground-based FTIR measurements which rather offer a mean to validate the (sub-)columnar NO_y budget and its temporal variations. Chemical modelling will be needed to estimate the concentration profile of the nitrogen oxides not measured by the envisaged validation system or to account for mismatches in the measurement times for these diurnally varying species.

4.2.4.2 Age of air (AoA)

Age-of-air calculations usually make use of modelled and/or observed data on long-lived species like SF₆, CFC-12, HCFC-22, CH₄, and/or N₂O. GLORIA-B balloon flights in Kiruna and Timmins have demonstrated that the payload can provide the needed profile measurements to calculate mean age of air profiles up to about 25 km. Verification of the age-of-air product can also make use of long-lived tracer correlations based on measurements by surface gas chromatography (AGAGE and HATS networks), airborne in situ samplers or (ground-, air- or space-based) FTIR spectrometers (e.g. the NDACC-IRWG network and the IASI(-NG) satellite series). These measurements and their interest for age-of-air validation are introduced in Section 5 of the document.

4.2.4.3 Gravity waves (GW)

Validation strategies for gravity wave parameters were investigated for the PREMIER mission concept and reported in ESA's Gravity Wave Study Validation Strategies Report by Hertzog et al. (December 2011). Although not the focus of the study, some updates can be found reported in the GWEX final report by Krisch et al. (April 2018). These detailed reports are cited for reference and will not be duplicated here, but a short

summary can be useful. The proposed strategies depend on the wavelength of the targeted GW and make use of complementary measurements of temperature, winds and other parameters, as well as meteorological analyses. Key measurement techniques include radiosondes, rocket-sondes, high-altitude aircrafts, temperature and wind lidars, and radars. The potential use and limitations of airglow imagers, of GPS radio occultations, and of nadir-viewing satellite observations in the millimetre wave domain (e.g., AMSU) and the infrared range (e.g., AIRS) are discussed as well. Several of these measurements are introduced in Sections 5 and 6 of this document.

5 Fiducial Reference Measurements and other validation sources in the CAIRT era

5.1 Ground-based measurements

5.1.1 Global monitoring networks

The ground-based validation of CAIRT will make use of traceable high-quality measurements acquired on a routine basis by ground- and balloon-based monitoring networks acknowledged as contributors to WMO's Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW), Global Climate Observing System (GCOS), and the upcoming Global Greenhouse Gas Watch (G3W):

- GCOS Reference Upper-Air Network (GRUAN), <https://www.gruan.org/>
- GAW ozone monitoring programme, data archived at the World Ozone and Ultraviolet Data Centre (WOUDC), <https://woudc.org/>
- Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change (NDACC), De Mazière *et al.* (2018), <https://www.ndacc.org/>
- Network for the Detection of Mesospheric Change (NDMC), Bittner *et al.* (2010), <https://ndmc.dlr.de/>
- NASA Southern Hemisphere Additional Ozone-sonde programme (SHADOZ), Thompson *et al.* (2017), <https://tropo.gsfc.nasa.gov/shadoz/>
- Advanced Global Atmospheric Gases Experiment (AGAGE), <https://agage.eas.gatech.edu/>
- NOAA Halocarbons and other Atmospheric Trace Species (HATS), <https://gml.noaa.gov/hats/>
- Pandonia Global Network (PGN), <https://www.pandonia-global-network.org/>
- Total Carbon Column Observing Network (TCCON), <https://www.tcon.caltech.edu>
- GAW Aerosol Lidar Observation Network (GALION), <https://galion.world/>
- NOAA's Balloon Baseline Stratospheric Aerosol Profiles (B²SAP), <https://csl.noaa.gov/projects/b2sap/>
- Sub-/agency networks and initiatives contributing to one or several of the aforementioned networks although with their own specific objectives (NOAA-ESRL, MATCH campaigns...)

5.1.2 Measurement techniques relevant to Level-2a products

Most of the relevant instruments affiliated with one of the listed networks and monitoring the vertical profile and/or column of CAIRT related species have demonstrated appropriateness for the validation of limb infrared satellites and have likely an appreciable level of CEOS-FRM maturity (although not assessed yet at the time of this report).

Ground-based remote sensing

- Rayleigh, sodium (Na) and potassium (Ka) temperature lidars
- Rayleigh-Mie Doppler wind lidar
- Differential ozone Absorption Lidar (DIAL, mainly NDACC)
- Fourier Transform Infra-Red solar spectrometry (FTIR, mainly NDACC solar mid-infrared)
- Millimetre wave emission and Doppler shift radiometry (MWR)
- Zenith-scattered-light UV-Visible DOAS spectrometry (ZLS-DOAS, mainly NDACC)
- Backscatter Rayleigh-Mie aerosol lidar (mainly NDACC)
- Direct-Sun UV-Visible DOAS spectrometry (DS-DOAS, including PGN)

- Airglow emissions infrared spectrometry (GRIPS, mainly NDMC)

Ballon-borne in-situ techniques

- AirCore (Tans (2009); Karion et al. (2010))
- Electrochemical cell ozonesonde
- PTU radiosonde (pressure, temperature and humidity)
- Cryogenic Frostpoint Hygrometer (CFH; Vömel et al. 2007)
- NOAA Frost Point Hygrometer (FPH; Hurst et al., 2011)
- Portable Optical Particle Spectrometry (POPS)

5.1.3 Measurement techniques relevant to Level-2b products

As examples of validation comparisons possible for Level-2b products, FTIR spectrometers can provide coincident measurements of several trace gases enabling an independent derivation of the reactive nitrogen budget NO_y (e.g., Lindenmaier et al., 2011) and long-lived tracer correlations related to the age-of-air (e.g., Douglass et al., 2017; Strahan et al., 2020).

In the case of long-lived tracers, surface measurements obtained by gas chromatography networks and airborne experiments have also been helpful in validating some aspects of Level-2 data quality if converted into a total column estimate or if used to scale a known vertical profile. In particular, NOAA's AGAGE and HATS monitoring programmes measure surface concentrations of CAIRT long-lived species like SF₆, CFC-11, CFC-12, HCFC-22, N₂O, CO and OCS. The surface measurements from these programmes are often used as a tropospheric reference for age-of-air product calculations and will be helpful in assessing the quality of CAIRT age-of-air products. The long-term time series of surface measurements will also be useful for examining trends in CAIRT long-lived species.

The profiling of gravity-wave-related temperature variations by radiosondes and by Rayleigh, sodium and potassium lidars, and of related wind variations by Rayleigh-Mie Doppler lidars and by Doppler microwave radiometers, can contribute to the validation of these Level-2b products (Dawkins et al., 2018).

5.1.4 Overview of validation capabilities for each Level-2a species

Table 4 gives an overview of the ground- and balloon-based monitoring capabilities that should be considered as appropriate CAIRT validation sources. A complete description of the current capabilities is beyond the scope of this document, however,

Figure 1 gives an idea of the range and vertical resolution achieved by the instrumentation currently in operation in the Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change (NDACC, <https://www.ndacc.org>). The geographical distribution of stations in a network varies from one technique and one species to another. The following figures display the current geographical distribution of stations for:

- GRUAN light-weight balloons measuring the temperature and water vapour profiles from the ground up to 30 km (Figure 2),
- NDACC Rayleigh-scatter, sodium resonance and potassium lidars measuring the stratospheric and mesospheric temperature profile (Figure 3),
- Infrared airglow emissions spectrometers measuring mesopause temperature (Figure 4),

- NDACC microwave radiometers measuring the water vapour mixing ratio profile in the 25-70 km range (Figure 5),
- NDACC stratospheric ozone lidars (DIAL, ozone density profile from 15 to 45-48 km) and microwave ozone radiometers (ozone VMR from 25 to 70 km) (Figure 6),
- NDACC FTIR spectrometers measuring low-resolution profiles of O₃, CH₄, N₂O and CO, and vertical columns of SF₆, CFC-11, CFC-12, HCFC-22, NO₂, HNO₃, ClONO₂, PAN, OCS and other species (Figure 7),
- AGAGE network (Figure 8) and HATS (Figure 9) and HATS programme stations measuring by gas chromatography with detection by mass spectrometry the near-surface abundance of SF₆, HCFC-22, CFC-11, CFC-12, N₂O, and other long-lived species,
- NDACC zenith-scattered-light UV-visible DOAS spectrometers retrieving stratospheric NO₂ profiles in the context of ESA's FRM4DOAS central processing project (Figure 10),
- NDACC aerosol backscatter lidars, NOAA/B2SAP balloon-borne optical particle spectrometers and GAW Aerosol Lidar Observation Network (GALION), measuring aerosols at least at the lowest altitudes of CAIRT and valuable to detect fires, volcanic eruptions and geoenengineering events (Figure 11).

Figure 1 - Observational capabilities of NDACC relevant to CAIRT Level-2(+) validation. Ripples indicate approximate vertical resolution. (CAIRT dedicated adaptation of the official NDACC Observational Capabilities chart available on <https://ndacc.org>).

Table 4 – Ground- and balloon-based instruments suitable for the validation of CAIRT Level-2 data: CAIRT product, covered altitude regions, measurement technique, vertical resolution compared to that of CAIRT, network affiliation. G and T are for Goal and Threshold resolution requirements, respectively; DFS is approximate Degree of Freedom of the Signal.

Product	Regions	Instrument technique	Vertical resolution	Networks / Remarks
T	FT-MS MS-UM mesopause UM-LT	PTU radiosonde Rayleigh lidar Airglow infrared spectrometer Na and K resonance lidars	Higher Similar (G) Lower - similar (T) Similar (G)	GRUAN, WMO WWW NDACC-LidarWG NDMC
H ₂ O	FT-LS FT-LS FT-LS LS-LM	PTU radiosonde CFH and FHP sondes Solar mid-infrared FTIR Microwave radiometry	Higher Higher Lower (DFS < 3) Lower	GRUAN, WMO WWW GRUAN, NDACC NDACC-IRWG NDACC-MWR
O ₃	FT-MS FT-US UT-US LS-LM	Ozone sonde Solar mid-infrared FTIR Stratospheric DIAL Microwave radiometry	Higher Lower (DFS 3 - 5) Similar (T) Lower (8 - 12 km)	WMO GAW, NDACC, SHADOZ... NDACC-IRWG / diurnal cycle NDACC-LidarWG NDACC-MWR
CH ₄	FT (surf.) FT-MS FT-US TC	Gas chromatography Laser diode analyser Solar mid-infrared FTIR Solar near-infrared FTIR	Surface Higher - similar (G) Lower (DFS 2.5 - 3.5) Total column	AGAGE, HATS AirCore NDACC-IRWG TCCON, COCCON
SF ₆	FT (surf.) FT-MS TC	Gas chromatography Laser diode analyser Solar mid-infrared FTIR	Surface Higher - similar (G) Total column (DFS 1)	AGAGE, HATS AirCore NDACC-IRWG
HCFC-22	FT (surf.) TC	Gas chromatography Solar mid-infrared FTIR	Surface Total column (DFS 1)	AGAGE, HATS NDACC-IRWG
CFC-11	FT (surf.) FT-MS TC	Gas chromatography Laser diode analyser Solar mid-infrared FTIR	Surface Higher - similar (G) Total column (DFS 1)	AGAGE, HATS AirCore NDACC-IRWG
CFC-12	FT (surf.) FT-MS TC	Gas chromatography Laser diode analyser Solar mid-infrared FTIR	Surface Higher - similar (G) Total column (DFS 1)	AGAGE, HATS AirCore NDACC-IRWG
N ₂ O	FT (surf.) FT-MS FT-US LS-US	Gas chromatography Laser diode analyser Solar mid-infrared FTIR Microwave radiometry	Surface Higher - similar (G) Lower (DFS 3 - 5) Similar (T)	AGAGE, HATS AirCore NDACC-IRWG NDACC, ceased operation
CO	FT (surf.) FT-US MS-UM MS-LM TC	Gas chromatography Solar mid-infrared FTIR Solar mid-infrared FTIR Microwave radiometry Solar near-infrared FTIR	Surface Lower (DFS 2.5 - 4) Lower (DFS ~ 1) Similar (T) Total column	AGAGE, HATS NDACC-IRWG NDACC, specific retrieval NDACC, ceased operation TCCON, COCCON
NO	FT-LM LS-LT	Solar mid-infrared FTIR Solar mid-infrared FTIR	Lower (DFS ~ 1 - 2) Lower (DFS 1 - 2.8)	NDACC, specific retrieval NDACC, specific retrieval
NO ₂	FT-US LS-US TC	Zenith-sky UVVIS DOAS Solar mid-infrared FTIR Direct-Sun UVVIS DOAS	Lower (DFS 2 - 3) Lower (DFS < 2) Total column	NDACC-UVVIS FRM4DOAS NDACC-IRWG, diurnal cycle PGN
HNO ₃	FT-US LS-US	Solar mid-infrared FTIR Microwave radiometry	Lower (DFS 2.5 - 4) Lower	NDACC-IRWG NDACC, ceased operation
N ₂ O ₅	TC	Lunar mid-infrared FTIR	Total column	Campaign, night-time only
ClONO ₂	TC	Solar mid-infrared FTIR	Total column (DFS 1)	NDACC-IRWG
PAN	FT (surf.)	Gas chromatography	Surface	HATS
OCS	FT (surf.) TC	Gas chromatography Solar mid-infrared FTIR	Surface Lower (DFS ~ 2.5)	AGAGE, HATS NDACC-IRWG
SO ₂	TC	Direct-Sun UVVIS DOAS	Total column	PGN

Temperature and water vapour

From free troposphere up to middle stratosphere

Figure 2 - Geographical distribution of GCOS Reference Upper-Air Network (GRUAN) measuring the T and H₂O profile from the ground up to 30 km. Figure from the GRUAN website <https://www.gruan.org/>

Temperature

From middle stratosphere up to lower thermosphere

Figure 3 - NDACC Rayleigh-scatter (green circles, T profile from 30 to 80-95 km), sodium resonance (orange, T profile from 80 to 110 km) and potassium (grey, T profile from 80 to 110 km) temperature lidars. Background: example ECMWF temperature map at 8 hPa.

Temperature

Mesopause temperature

Figure 4 – Geographical distribution of the Network for the Detection of Mesospheric Change (NDMC) infrared spectrometers measuring air glow emissions from excited OH* and O* radicals and excited O₂ to retrieve the mesopause temperature from rotational P-branch transitions in the Meinel band around 1.55 μm (Bittner et al., 2010). Figure from the NDMC website <https://ndmc.dlr.de>

Water vapour

From low stratosphere up to mesosphere

Figure 5 - Geographical distribution of NDACC microwave radiometers measuring the water vapour mixing ratio profile in the 25-75 km range. Background: BASCOE assimilation of MIPAS water vapour VMR at 1 hPa.

Ozone

From low stratosphere up to middle mesosphere

Figure 6 - Geographical distribution of NDACC lidars (green circles, ozone density profile from 15 to 45-50 km) and millimetre-wave radiometers (red circles, ozone VMR from 25 to 70 km). Background: BASCOE assimilation of MIPAS ozone VMR at 30 hPa.

O₃, CH₄, N₂O, CO, SF₆, CFCs...

Low-resolution profile and vertical column

Figure 7 - Geographical distribution of NDACC FTIR spectrometers offering measurement capabilities for low-resolution profiles of O₃, CH₄, N₂O, CO, and the vertical column of SF₆, HCFC-22, CFC-11, CFC-12, NO₂, HNO₃, ClONO₂, PAN, OCS and other species. Background: BASCOE assimilation of MIPAS CH₄ VMR at 10 hPa.

SF₆, HCFC-22, CFC-11, CFC-12, N₂O, and other long-lived species

AGAGE: Near-surface measurements convertible into partial columns and age-of-air

NDACC FTIR: column/profile measurements

CAIRT Validation - SF6 Profile - AGAGE & FTIR NDACC

Figure 8 - Geographical distribution of AGAGE stations (green circles) measuring near-surface abundance of SF₆, HCFC-22, CFC-11/12, CH₄, N₂O, and other long-lived trace gases, and of NDACC FTIR stations (red circles) at which columns/profiles of the same species can be retrieved. Background: BASCOE simulation of SF₆ VMR at 50 hPa.

SF₆, HCFC-22, CFC-11, CFC-12, N₂O, COS, and other long-lived species

HATS: Near-surface measurements convertible into partial columns and age-of-air

Figure 9 - Geographical distribution of HATS programme measuring near-surface abundance of near-surface abundance of SF₆, CFCs, HCFCs, N₂O, OCS, and other long-lived trace gases. Figure from HATS website <https://gml.noaa.gov/hats/>

Stratospheric NO₂

Low-resolution profile and vertical column

Figure 10 - Geographical distribution of NDACC-UVIS zenith-scattered-light DOAS spectrometers offering measurement capabilities for low-resolution profiles of NO₂ and contributing to ESA's FRM4DOAS harmonization and central processing project. Background: example map of Sentinel-5P TROPOMI stratospheric NO₂ column (contains modified Copernicus data reprocessed at BIRA-IASB).

Aerosols

From troposphere up to middle stratosphere

Figure 11 – Top: NDACC backscatter lidars (squares, aerosol backscatter and extinction from 8 km up to 30-50 km) and NOAA/B2SAP balloon-borne optical particle spectrometers (circles, aerosol number density and size distributions from ground up to 30 km) able to detect stratospheric aerosols and Polar Stratospheric Clouds. Bottom: GAW Aerosol Lidar Observation Network (GALION) gathering several lidar measurement types reaching at least the lowest altitudes of CAIRT and valuable to detect fires, volcanic eruptions and geoengineering events.

5.2 Satellite missions

CAIRT is planned as an explorer mission filling a critical gap in the global observing system of high-resolution profilers for atmospheric composition and dynamics. Its launch is envisaged in an era when only a few limb and solar occultation profilers might operate, as illustrated in Figure 12 giving an overview of the limb and solar occultation missions in the 2000-2040 timeframe. To date, only the JPSS OMPS-limb operational ozone profilers on board of the future NOAA-22 and NOAA-23 platforms will likely offer opportunities for satellite-to-satellite ozone profile comparisons at similar vertical resolution. The planned Canadian HAWC mission will also provide water vapour and aerosol profiles focusing on the UTLS region. If extended in time the ALTIUS mission could also provide opportunities for O₃, H₂O, NO₂, temperature and aerosol data intercomparisons. The chance to have SCISAT-1 (ACE-FTS and MAESTRO) and SABER TIMED instruments still operating in that timeframe is extremely unlikely.

The current planning of future high-resolution profilers is thus by far insufficient to cover the CAIRT validation needs, and especially in terms of measured species. Therefore, low-resolution nadir sounders must be envisaged as well. To ensure continuity, additional efforts need to be taken to connect current and planned missions to the CAIRT era.

Figure 12 – Solar occultation (top) and limb emission/scattering missions (bottom) in the 2000-2040 timeframe. The colour code refers to the spectral range of the instrument. The vertical dashed line indicates current days, and the shaded area a working time frame for CAIRT. Last updates on missions collected from CEOS WGCV-ACSG.

5.2.1 ACE-FTS temperature, O_3 , H_2O , CH_4 , SF_6 , CFCs, ..., NO_y , Age of Air

A SWIR/MWIR/TIR mission with the SCISAT-1 ACE-FTS capabilities is particularly well suited since it measures all the CAIRT species at comparable vertical resolution, although on a high-inclination orbit of 74° and in solar occultation mode which combine to offer sparse latitude-time sampling (see Figure 10). In addition to the numerous trace gases, an age-of-air product has recently been derived from ACE-FTS (Saunders et al., 2025, doi:10.5194/acp-25-4185-2025) that can be useful for validating the CAIRT Level-2b age-of-air product.

The “self-calibrating” nature of the solar occultation technique used by ACE-FTS can provide an advantage as the data set is less susceptible to measurement drifts. While ACE has been in orbit for more than 22 years, it will not last forever. To bridge between current ACE-FTS and future CAIRT measurements, it is recommended to plan a series of balloon campaigns as a transfer between these missions, at least for primary mission targets like SF_6 , N_2O and CFCs.

Figure 13 – Latitude-time progression of solar occultation events over one year as observed by ACE-FTS from its high-inclination orbit of 74° .

5.2.2 SABER temperature, O_3 , H_2O , NO , gravity waves

The Sounding of the Atmosphere using Broadband Emission Radiometry (SABER) instrument is a 10-channel broadband infrared radiometer covering the spectral range from $1.27 \mu\text{m}$ to $16 \mu\text{m}$. Operating on board of NASA's TIMED (Thermosphere Ionosphere Mesosphere Energetics Dynamics) satellite on a 74° -inclination orbit the instrument scans the atmospheric limb from 15 km up to 400 km and provides global measurements. These measurements are used to retrieve from the stratosphere up to the lower thermosphere the vertical distribution of kinetic temperature, pressure, geopotential height, volume mixing ratio for O_3 , H_2O , NO , CO_2 , and many other parameters. Operating since January 2002 the instrument monitors temperature with a long-term stability of 0.2 K per decade in the stratosphere and has provided unique data records of changes in atmospheric composition and gravity waves. Despite its excellent long-term performance it is unlikely that the mission will still operate in the CAIRT timeframe. To bridge between current SABER and future CAIRT temperature data in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere it is recommended to plan regular acquisition of profile measurements by ground-based sodium, potassium and Rayleigh lidars (Section 5.1, Figure 3) as a transfer between these missions, as well as stratospheric and mesospheric H_2O (Figure 5) and O_3 (Figure 6) profile measurements by ground-based microwave radiometry.

5.2.3 ALTIUS H_2O , O_3 , NO_2 , temperature, aerosols

Atmospheric Limb Tracker for Investigation of the Upcoming Stratosphere (ALTIUS) is an atmospheric ozone profiling mission proposed by BIRA-IASB and developed by ESA as part of its Earth Watch programme. Mounted on a PROBA platform, the ALTIUS instrument consists of a UV-VIS-NIR imaging spectrometer optimised to measure solar radiation scattered by the Earth's limb and also in solar and stellar occultation modes. With a mission lifetime of minimum 3 years, ALTIUS will continue the essential climate data record on stratospheric ozone and aerosols started in the 1980s with the SAGE series and extended with UARS, ACE, Envisat, Aura and Odin. Its limb-viewing geometry on a polar orbit will be particularly valuable in providing daily global measurements to data assimilation systems like the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) Integrated Forecast System (IFS) and the Belgian Assimilation System of Chemical Observations (BASCOE). The launch of ALTIUS is currently planned in 2027-2028, which means that this mission could serve for cross-validations with CAIRT only if extended into the CAIRT mission time frame.

5.2.4 OMPS-LP O_3 , H_2O , aerosols

The Ozone Mapper and Profiler Suite (OMPS) series of instruments constitute the long-term satellite ozone monitoring programme of the US. OMPS limb (LP) and nadir (NM/NP) instruments operate currently aboard the polar satellites Suomi NPP, NOAA-20 and NOAA-21, and they are scheduled to continue on the Joint Polar Satellite System (JPSS)-3 and -4 missions until nominally 2041. Part of the OMPS suite the OMPS-LP limb ozone profiler provides primarily ozone and aerosol profile data. It is likely that at least one OMPS-LP mission will cover the CAIRT timeframe. OMPS-LP constitutes a natural candidate for cross-validations with CAIRT.

5.2.5 HAWC H_2O , aerosols

The Canadian-led High-altitude Aerosols, Water vapour, and Clouds (HAWC, Langille et al., 2025) mission is planned for launch in 2031 to investigate the UTLS and should be operating within the CAIRT time frame. Spatial Heterodyne Observations of Water (SHOW) will measure water vapour in the tropopause region with high vertical and spatial resolution. This will be very valuable for cross-validation of CAIRT's water vapour profiles in its lower altitude region. Multi-spectral measurements of aerosol extinction will be provided by the Aerosol Limb Imager (ALI). With a wider wavelength range than OMPS-LP, ALI visible and near-infrared data sets will yield highly complementary information to that from CAIRT. This will provide useful opportunities for validation investigations of these aerosol profiles.

5.2.6 SAGE-III H_2O , O_3 , NO_2 , aerosols

Stratospheric Aerosol and Gas Experiment (SAGE) uses the solar occultation technique to measure the stratospheric and UT/LS profile of atmospheric ozone, aerosol extinction, water vapour and nitrogen dioxide. Since 2017 the SAGE-III instrument operates aboard the International Space Station (ISS). The instrument is in good health and can operate as long as the ISS remains operational. It is however improbable that the ISS will extend operation until the CAIRT time frame. Forming with the previous SAGE and SAGE-II missions an invaluable long-term reference for its main four products, it is highly desired to connect the SAGE-III data record to CAIRT using balloon-based measurements as a transfer.

Figure 14 – Nadir-viewing missions on low-Earth polar (LEO) and geostationary (GEO) orbits in the 2000-2045 timeframe. Top: middle (MIR), thermal infrared (TIR) and short-wave infrared (SWIR) LEO sounders. Bottom: ultraviolet (UV), visible (VIS) and near-infrared (NIR) LEO spectrometers, some with a SWIR channel. Middle: UV-VIS-NIR and MIR-TIR sounders on geostationary orbits. Last updates on missions collected from CEOS WGCV-ACSG.

5.2.7 IASI-NG and CrIS temperature, O₃, H₂O, CH₄, SF₆, CFCs, N₂O, HNO₃...

Thermal infrared sounders measuring at nadir cannot offer the high vertical resolution of the limb profilers, however, they share commonalities with the spectral range of CAIRT and can provide global day/night coverage of several relevant molecules, although with a sensitivity peaking at lower altitudes than CAIRT (in the troposphere or UT/LS). Recent publications show e.g. that IASI SF₆ trends are in excellent agreement with AGAGE surface SF₆ trends and in good agreement with ACE-FTS SF₆ trends (De Longueville et al., JQSRT 2023).

In particular, the Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer - New Generation (IASI-NG) has the capability to measure temperature, ozone and water vapour profiles as well as columns or low-resolution profiles of most of the CAIRT trace gases: SF₆, CFCs, N₂O, CH₄, HNO₃, PAN, OCS and SO₂. Age of air and the NO_y budget can be derived from IASI-NG data with some modelling support as aforementioned. The proto-flight model of this instrument was launched on board of MetOp-SG-A1 in August 2025 and will be followed by two other missions, the second one planned for 2032-2040 having a probability to operate along the entire CAIRT timeframe. Relevant nadir thermal infrared sounders are shown in Figure 14.

Similarly, Cross-track Infrared Sounder (CrIS) is a nadir-viewing interferometer having the capability to provide global day/night coverage of several CAIRT molecules. The current CrIS mission on the NOAA-21 polar satellite and the following one planned for JPSS-4 have good probability to operate during the CAIRT time frame.

5.2.8 Geostationary infrared interferometers

Mid-wave and long-wave infrared interferometers mounted on geostationary satellites are also expected to operate during the CAIRT time frame: the MTG-S-1/2 IRS and the Chinese GIIRS-2. These missions are designed to give access to the entire diurnal cycle of the vertical column of relevant molecules over Europe and East-Asia, respectively, although with poor vertical resolution and a sensitivity peaking at lower altitudes than CAIRT. Based on the IASI heritage IRS and GIIRS-2 are nevertheless new developments, and it is premature to judge whether their data could serve in cross-validation studies with CAIRT.

5.2.9 SWIR nadir CH₄, CO

As shown in Figure 11, several nadir spectrometers working in the short-wave-infrared (SWIR) spectral range will measure the vertical column of CO₂, CH₄ and CO in the CAIRT time frame, including the Sentinel-5 UVNS and CO2M operational LEO missions. These missions have significantly different objectives than CAIRT. The poor vertical resolution and low-altitude sensitivity of the SWIR nadir technique makes these data hardly relevant to CAIRT validation. Their main advantage is the global coverage that these missions can achieve in one or a few days.

5.2.10 UV-VIS-NIR nadir O₃, NO₂, SO₂, clouds, aerosols

Figure 11 shows that several nadir spectrometers working in the ultraviolet (UV), visible (VIS) and near-infrared (NIR) spectral ranges will measure the ozone profile and the vertical column of several species in the CAIRT time frame, including the Sentinel-5 UVNS and JPSS OMPS-NM/NP operational LEO missions and the CEOS GEO-AQ constellation of geostationary air quality satellites (GEMS, TEMPO, and Sentinel-4 UVN). These missions have significantly different objectives than CAIRT and are less relevant to its validation than others as they measure different species and at poorer vertical resolution.

5.3 Balloon campaigns

5.3.1 Rationale and strategy

Instrumentation embarked on board of stratospheric balloons acquires relevant measurements at good vertical resolution and at altitudes usually from the UTLS up to the burst point/flight altitude of the balloon (~30-35 km). Depending on the deployed instrumentation balloon campaigns can offer views not only to the CAIRT measurand but also to the environment of the measurement, including influence quantities and ancillary parameters.

Balloon campaigns with traceable measurements are also a privileged transfer between high-resolution satellite missions, and in the present case, between CAIRT and its reference predecessor ACE-FTS. Therefore, it is recommended to plan such balloon campaigns in the coming years, before the termination (or loss) of ACE-FTS, and similar balloon measurements in the early phase of CAIRT measurements (when the quality of the Level-1b data has stabilized in phase E1 or early phase E2). These transfer campaigns should take place for different atmospheric states, and at least at low, middle and high latitudes. Special care should be given to their co-location with ACE-FTS overpasses to ensure appropriate comparison opportunities.

The next subsections introduce a non-exhaustive list of relevant following balloon experiments.

5.3.2 GLORIA-Lite

Gimballed Limb Observer for Radiance Imaging of the Atmosphere (GLORIA, Friedl-Vallon et al. 2014) is the airborne demonstrator of CAIRT. The instrument is a joint development of the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) and Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ). This Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer is designed to operate on various high altitude research platforms on aircraft and stratospheric balloons. GLORIA has been successfully flown on a number of aircraft campaigns and provides important background for experience with infra-red limb imaging and tomographic retrievals (GLORIA, <https://gloria.helmholtz.de/Publications.php>). GLORIA has been operated on the German research aircraft HALO and on the high-altitude aircraft Geophysica in the frame of seven campaigns since 2011. GLORIA-B, the balloon version of GLORIA, has been flown at altitudes of more than 35 km during two stratospheric balloon campaigns within the HEMERA Research Infrastructure funded by the Horizon 2020 framework Programme of the European Union: from Kiruna (Sweden) in August 2021, and from Timmins (Canada) in August 2022.

Based on the GLORIA heritage, GLORIA-Lite is a completely newly developed instrument. The significant reduction in size and weight through the use of the latest infrared sensors, customized electronics and innovative manufacturing techniques also enables the use on long-duration balloon flights (e.g., transatlantic). The heart of GLORIA-Lite is an imaging Fourier Transform Spectrometer that analyzes the infrared light emitted by more than 20 different molecules and aerosols in the atmosphere and calculates their concentrations. GLORIA-Lite was launched from Kiruna (Arctic Sweden) on board of a large stratospheric balloon on June 22, 2024, and flew at an altitude of 40 km from Kiruna to on Baffin Island (Canada), crossing over the North Atlantic and Greenland.

5.3.3 STRATOS

Since 2012, Canada has been involved in multiple STRATOS stratospheric campaigns during which dozens Canadian science experiments and technologies were flown on board of stratospheric balloons. The Canadian Space Agency (CSA), in collaboration with the French Space Agency (CNES), has provided stratospheric flight opportunities for payloads developed by industry and academia, as well as support and expert advice for payload preparation and integration. An example of relevant payload is the Canadian Atmospheric Tomography System (CATS). CATS can image vertical profiles of trace gases in the atmosphere, such as O₃ and NO₂. Another relevant payload is the SAOZ-balloon experiment, a UV-VIS solar occultation instrument measuring the vertical profile of NO₂, BrO, OClO, H₂O and O₃ from 10 up to about 30 km. In situ measurement systems, such as the Canadian Atmospheric Laser Absorption Spectrometer Experiment Testbed (CALASET), can provide vertical profiles of greenhouse gases (CO₂, N₂O, CH₄) during ascent of the balloon. STRATOS balloons usually are launched from the Timmins Stratospheric Balloon Base in Northern Ontario (Canada), but a few flights have also taken place also from Kiruna (Sweden) and Alice Springs (Australia).

5.3.4 AirCore

The AirCore atmospheric sampling system is a lightweight whole-air sampler that, flown on a small balloon, provides a means for retrieving calibrated, vertical profiles of trace gases. Comprised of a long, coiled tube, the AirCore relies on the fact that diffusion acts slowly within such a vessel, allowing for the preservation of an air sample and subsequent analysis on a calibrated continuous, laboratory-grade trace gas analyzer after balloon landing (Baier et al., 2023). The AirCore has been primarily used to measure CO₂ and CH₄, while ongoing experiments are establishing its application to the measurement of long-lived species of CAIRT interest such as SF₆, CFCs and other halocarbons, N₂O, and CO.

5.3.5 Additional water vapour, aerosols and ozone sondes

The aforementioned campaigns can also embark smaller instrumentation like FPH/CFH sondes for water vapour and several types of aerosol sondes including NOAA's POPS. Embarking these additional measurements as "piggy-back" on larger experiments is recommended to improve on the limited frequency of the current FPH/CFH and aerosol sondes programmes.

Dedicated measurement campaigns, using these water vapour and aerosol sondes, could be devised to focus on particular regions and seasons to support dedicated validation goals.

These campaigns could also be undertaken using ozonesondes, in a role different from the monitoring networks described above, e.g., to enhance measurement density in the Arctic or Antarctic winter and springtime and better validate CAIRT in ozone depletion conditions.

5.4 Aircraft campaigns

Instrumentation can also be embarked on board research aircraft to acquire relevant measurements at good vertical resolution primarily focusing in the UTLS near the flight altitude. Depending on the deployed instrumentation, aircraft campaigns can provide complementary measurements of CAIRT measurands (e.g., Level-2a products) and of derived products (Level-2b). For example, dedicated airborne measurements from the GLORIA instrument and in situ sensors can provide high spatial resolution validation measurements for trace gases in the highly structured UTLS region. Airborne lidar temperature profiles, from an instrument such as ALIMA, can be used to derive gravity wave characteristics for comparison with CAIRT-derived gravity wave parameters.

6 Tools and infrastructures

6.1 Tools

6.1.1 ESA Atmospheric Toolbox

ESA's Atmospheric Toolbox (<https://atmospherictoolbox.org/>) aims to support the validation and user community with tools for ingesting, processing, and analyzing atmospheric remote sensing data. It contains the CODA and HARP toolsets developed to provide a harmonised interface for reading and pre-processing data from a wide range of atmospheric data products. CAIRT relevant features are the capability to create gridded Level-3 data and perform inter-comparisons in support of validation. The software consists of command line tools and interfaces for e.g. Python, C, MATLAB, and IDL. The toolbox currently supports satellite products from TROPOMI (Sentinel-5 Precursor), EarthCARE, ALADIN (Aeolus), GOME-2 and IASI (MetOp), and OMI (Aura), as well as ground based and model data. Further adaptation of CODA and HARP to CAIRT is recommended to facilitate the uptake of CAIRT data in validation activities and scientific applications.

6.1.2 CAIRT overpass and measurement predictor

An overpass and measurement predictor tool is needed by the validation measurement teams predisposed to better coordinate their measurements with the CAIRT observations. Such a tool is especially useful for the coordinated launch of balloon-borne ozonesondes and PTU radiosondes which, otherwise, are launched according to other operational criteria or local habits. Such a tool may also be useful for the planning of the lidar measurements, not always performed every day due to their logistical costs and needs, and for the planning of validation campaigns. Ideally an overpass and measurement predictor shall predict the central geolocation and local time of the air masses that will be probed by CAIRT.

A natural candidate is ESA's Earth observation Swath and Orbit Visualisation tool (ESOV, <https://eop-cfi.esa.int/index.php/applications/esov>). ESOV NG functions include visualization of instrument swaths, ground tracks, zone coverages, and ground Station visibility. ESOV NG can generate overpass tables for a list of atmospheric composition satellites including Envisat, ERS-2, ADM-Aeolus, MetOp, MetOp-SG, EarthCARE, and Sentinel-5P. Further update of ESOV NG to CAIRT is recommended.

6.1.3 Trajectory tools

Forward prediction and backward analysis trajectory tools like FLEXTRA and HYSPLIT simulate simple air parcel trajectories using meteorological forecasts or reanalysis, respectively. Prediction trajectory tools are helpful in planning measurement campaigns with optimized air mass co-location and identification of the upcoming atmospheric state. Backward trajectory tools are helpful in understanding the context of a past validation campaign and in interpreting the data comparisons.

6.2 Infrastructures

6.2.1 CAIRT Validation Data Centre

Establishing a central validation data centre for CAIRT is recommended for various purposes:

- to make a one-stop shop for all CAIRT validation data,
- to mirror official FRM monitoring networks data archives and ensure continuity of data access,
- to archive validation measurements not contributing to monitoring networks and not archived in other data centres,
- to ensure QA/QC and proper versioning of validation data reprocessings (data acquired and delivered during the commissioning phase are not always optimally calibrated and may need reprocessing after improved calibration),
- to support balloon-, aircraft-based and other validation and calibration campaigns and archive their data and metadata,
- to provide supporting services, e.g., automated overpass prediction for selected sites, and automated provision of meteorological maps (potential vorticity, temperature, PSC formation probability...) based on ECMWF forecasts,
- to support validation activities that will be proposed by the scientific community in response to a potential ESA Announcement of Opportunity (AO) for the Cal/Val of CAIRT.

ESA's Atmospheric Validation Data Centre (EVDC) operated at NILU (Norway) is the most natural candidate for archiving, versioning and sharing validation data. It has a long heritage as the validation centre for e.g. Envisat and it is currently used operationally for the routine validation of Sentinel-5P TROPOMI, in the framework of the ESA/Copernicus Atmosphere Mission Performance Cluster (ATM-MPC). Ground-based data sets suitable for TROPOMI validation are collected automatically from official archives of monitoring networks through mirroring. In particular, temperature and ozone profile data are collected from NDACC, the MATCH campaigns, SHADOZ, TOLNET, WOUDC; aerosol data from EARLINET; and cloud data from ACTRIS-CLOUDNET. An EVDC data policy is enforced through the signature of a protocol, requiring adherence to the data policy of the various data providers.